

Crystal structure study and catalytic application of Cu^{II} complexes derived from acylpyrazolone Schiff bases

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Manuscript received online 23 August 2016, accepted 18 September 2016

Abstract : Single crystal XRD study of copper complex of acylpyrazolone Schiff base ligand was carried out and it reveals that the complex can exist in square planar geometry. The crystal structure is triclinic with space group *P*-1 and cell parameters : *a* = 12.9460(5) Å, *b* = 13.9454(5) Å, *c* = 13.9454(5) Å, *Z* = 2, *R*₁ = 0.0431 and *wR*₂ = 0.1183. Both the ligands are coordinated in anti conformation creating two six-membered chelate rings. The Cu^{II} complexes were successfully used as catalysts for the solvent free oxidation of styrene and benzyl alcohol.

Keywords : Crystal structure, pyrazolone, Schiff base, copper complex, catalysis.

Introduction

Schiff bases (imines) constitute one of the most widely used families of organic compounds, not only as synthetic intermediates but also in coordination chemistry. Schiff base ligands are easily synthesized and form complexes with almost all metal ions¹⁻⁴. Acylpyrazolones are an interesting class of β-diketone compounds which can form a variety of Schiff bases and are reported to be superior reagents in biological, clinical and analytical applications⁵⁻⁸. Due to the presence of one oxygen and one nitrogen donor atoms and facile amine-one and imine-one tautomerism, they easily coordinate with metal ions after deprotonation of the enolic hydrogen and provide stable metal complexes with six-membered chelate rings⁹.

The interest in the coordination chemistry of pyrazolone Schiff bases and their various applications has increased greatly in the last decade¹⁰⁻¹⁵. However, very less attention has been paid on the use of pyrazolone Schiff base complexes as catalyst for the organic transformations. Only a few reports are available in the literatures for the use of pyrazolone Schiff base complexes as catalysts¹⁶⁻¹⁸.

Previously, we have reported the synthesis and DNA binding study of copper complexes of some Schiff bases

derived from acylpyrazolone ligands¹⁹. In this report crystal structure study of the copper complex of Schiff base of acylpyrazolone ligand was carried out and found that the complexes can also exist in the square planar geometry, which is in contrast to our previous report¹⁹. The catalytic properties of the copper(II) complexes have been thoroughly studied, in the hydrogen peroxide promoted solvent free oxidation of styrene and benzyl alcohol, under homogeneous conditions.

Results and discussion

Crystal structure of the complex :

The structure of the title compound is illustrated in Fig. 1. The structural details of other two complexes are provided in supplementary information. The single crystal X-ray diffraction study on complex clearly indicates that coordination around Cu^{II} is plane quadrilateral, coordinated by two oxygen atoms and two imido group nitrogen atoms from the two Schiff base ligands. Thus both the ligands form two six member chelate rings with the copper metal centre (Fig. 1).

Interestingly, in the crystal structure of the complex **1**, coordinated water molecules were eliminated and one acetonitrile molecule has appeared in the crystal lattice.

Fig. 1. ORTEP view of complex **1** with displacement ellipsoids drawn at 50% probability level.

This is in contrast to our previous reported structure (octahedral geometry) of the same complex¹⁹. The elimination of weakly coordinated water molecules might have taken place due to the heating of acetonitrile solution of complex **1**, which we used for obtaining X-ray diffraction quality single crystals by slow evaporation of the solution of the complex. Both the ligands are in *anti* conformation to each other, coordinated nitrogen atoms and oxygen atoms of both the ligands are *trans* to each other. Fig. 2 depicts crystal packing of the complex **1**.

The Cu^{II} has a distorted {O₂N₂} square planar environment with six different bond lengths. Selected bond lengths and bond angles are listed in Table 2. The bite angles O1-Cu1-N21 and O2-Cu1-N52 are 95.70(7)° and 94.93(7)°, respectively. The bond lengths of Cu1-O1 and Cu1-O2 are found to be 1.9045(14) Å and 1.9113(15) Å, respectively, while the bond lengths of Cu1-N21 and Cu1-N52 are found to be 1.9838(16) Å and 1.9758(16) Å, respectively. It is clear from the data that bond lengths of Cu-N bonds are greater than the bond lengths for Cu-O bonds in the complex. After the complexation with Cu^{II} the bond lengths O1-C5 and O2-C36 of the ligands were increased from 1.254(2) Å to 1.275(2) Å and 1.278(2) Å, respectively⁶. The bond lengths N21-C13 and N52-C44

Fig. 2. Crystal packing of the complex **1** (view down the *c* axis). Solvent molecule and H atoms were omitted for clarity.

of the ligands were decreased from 1.339(3) Å to 1.315(3) Å and 1.320(3) Å, respectively. The bond lengths N21-C22 and N52-C44 of the ligands were increased from 1.426(3) Å to 1.447(3) Å and 1.440(3) Å, respectively.

The bond angles C13-N21-C22 and C44-N52-C53 of ligands were decreased from 127.6(2) to 119.1(2) and 118.9(2), respectively, after complexation with copper(II). The bond angle N21-Cu1-N52 (142.87(7)) is greater than the bond angle O1-Cu1-O2 (149.32(8)). The Schiff base ligand of acylpyrazolones exists in the amine-one form in solid state, while after complexation they tautomerises in imine-ol form (Fig. 3).

Catalytic activity studies :

Oxidation of benzyl alcohol using Cu^{II} complexes :

The oxidation of benzyl alcohol, catalyzed by Cu^{II} complexes was carried out using H₂O₂ as an oxidant to give benzaldehyde, benzoic acid and benzyl benzoate as products. The formation of all these products is represented by Scheme 1. These are common products and have been identified by others as well^{21,22}.

The oxidation of benzyl alcohols was carried out in solvent free condition. The reaction conditions were

Fig. 3. Changes in the bond lengths of Schiff base ligand after complexation with Cu^{II}.

Scheme 1. Representation of benzyl alcohol oxidation and its products.

adopted from our previous report²⁴. The optimum condition for the maximum % conversion as well as selectivity for the oxidation of benzyl alcohol to benzaldehyde is reaction temperature (90 °C), benzyl alcohol (10 mmol), 30% H₂O₂ (30 mmol), catalyst amount (0.045 mmol) and reaction time (24 h). The progress of the reaction was monitored by GC-MS analysis and products formed in the reactions were matched with those reported in the literature.

The objective of the present study was to compare the reactivity of copper complexes of Schiff bases of acylpyrazolone ligands for the oxidation of benzyl alcohol. Thus, all three complexes were used as a catalyst for the oxidation of benzyl alcohol under the same reaction conditions. From the reaction data (Table 3) we could observe that the complex 2 shows 86% conversion in compare to complexes 1 and 3 which show 80% and 83% conversion. The complex 1 shows 90% selectivity for the benzaldehyde, while the complex 2 and 3 shows 87% and 89% selectivity for the benzaldehyde.

Table 1. Crystal data and structure refinement details for the complex 1

	Complex 1
Empirical formula	C ₅₆ H ₄₄ N ₆ O ₂ Cu·CH ₃ CN
Formula weight	937.57
Temp. (K)	293(2)
Crystal color and size (mm ³)	Brown, 0.3×0.2×0.2
Theta range for data collection (θ)	3.11 < θ < 65.00
Crystal system, space group	Triclinic, <i>P</i> -1
<i>a</i> (Å)	12.9460(5)
<i>b</i> (Å)	13.9454(5)
<i>c</i> (Å)	13.9454(5)
α (°)	68.737(4)
β (°)	67.769(4)
γ (°)	68.977(4)
Volume (Å ³)	2391.32(16)
Z	2
Calcd. density (mg m ⁻³)	1.302
Radiation	Cu Kα (λ = 1.54184)
Reflections collected/unique	15791/8108
Final R	0.0431
R _w (F ²)	0.1183
F (000)	978.0
GOF	1.032
Final residual electron density (e Å ⁻³)	-0.263 < Δρ < 0.370
CCDC No.	1007668

Oxidation of styrene using Cu^{II} complexes :

The oxidation of styrene, catalyzed by Cu^{II} complexes was carried out using H₂O₂ as an oxidant to give benzaldehyde, styreneoxide and benzoic acid as products. The formation of all these products is represented by Scheme 2. These are common products and have been identified

Scheme 2. Representation of styrene oxidation and its products.

by others as well^{22,24}. However, benzaldehyde was characterized as the major oxidation product in the present case. The oxidation of benzyl alcohols was carried out in solvent free condition. The reaction conditions were adopted from our previous report²⁵. In the present case, styrene (10 mmol), 30% H₂O₂ (30 mmol) and catalyst (20 mg) were taken in a 50 ml round-bottom flask and the reaction mixture was heated at 80 °C for 24 h. After

completion of the reaction the products were extracted in the hexane. % Conversion, % selectivity and turn-over number are presented in the Table 4.

Complexes **1**, **2** and **3** are showing 37, 59 and 41% conversion and 100, 90 and 97% selectivity for the benzaldehyde, respectively. The results reveals that complex **2** shows better conversion of styrene as compare to other two complexes, but shows only 90% selectivity for benzaldehyde, whereas, complex **1** show less conversion of styrene, but better selectivity (100%) for the benzaldehyde.

Experimental

Materials and physical measurements :

All reagents and solvents were purchased from commercial sources and were further purified by standard methods, if necessary²⁰. Styrene, benzyl alcohol, hexane, acetonitrile and 30% aqueous H₂O₂ were purchased from Merck and used as received. The copper(II) complexes were synthesized by the previous reported procedure¹⁹. Elemental analysis of C, H and N were determined using a Perkin-Elmer series-II 2400 elemental analyzer. Gravimetric and volumetric analysis were performed for the determination of copper after decomposition of complex in nitric acid. GC-MS analysis was carried out using gas chromatograph mass spectrometer (Agilent 5975 GC/MSD with 7890A GC system) having HP-5 capillary column of 60 m length and 250 μm diameter with a programmed oven temperature from 50 to 280 °C, at 1 mL min⁻¹ flow rate of He as a carrier gas and ion source at 230 °C.

Table 2. Selected bond lengths (Å) and bond angles (°) for complex **1**

Bond angles (°)		Bond lengths (Å)	
O1-Cu1-O2	142.87(7)	Cu1-O1	1.9045(14)
N21-Cu-N52	149.32(8)	Cu1-O2	1.9113(15)
O1-Cu1-N21	95.70(7)	Cu1-N21	1.9838(16)
O1-Cu1-N52	93.92(7)	Cu1-N52	1.9758(16)
O2-Cu1-N52	94.93(7)	O1-C5	1.275(2)
O2-Cu1-N21	94.77(7)	Cu1-O1	1.9045(14)
Cu1-O1-C5	121.7(1)	O2-C36	1.278(2)
Cu1-O2-C36	122.1(2)	N21-C13	1.315(3)
Cu1-N21-C13	125.7(1)	N52-C44	1.320(3)
Cu1-N52-C44	126.3(4)	N21-C22	1.447(3)
C13-N21-C22	119.1(2)	N52-C44	1.440(3)
C44-N52-C53	118.9(2)		
Cu1-N21-C22	115.1(1)		
Cu1-N52-C53	114.6(1)		

Table 3. Catalytic activity of Cu^{II} complexes towards the oxidation of benzyl alcohol

Catalyst	Substrate	Product	% Conversion of benzyl alcohol	% Selectivity of benzaldehyde	TON
Complex 1	Benzyl alcohol	Benzaldehyde	80	90	229
Complex 2	Benzyl alcohol	Benzaldehyde	86	87	240
Complex 3	Benzyl alcohol	Benzaldehyde	83	89	246

Table 4. Catalytic activity of Cu^{II} complexes towards the oxidation of styrene

Catalyst	Substrate	Product	% Conversion of benzyl alcohol	% Selectivity of benzaldehyde	TON
Complex 1	Styrene	Benzaldehyde	37	100	229
Complex 2	Styrene	Benzaldehyde	59	90	240
Complex 3	Styrene	Benzaldehyde	41	97	246

Crystal structure study of complex 1 :

The complex **1** was dissolved in acetonitrile and heated till the solution become clear and then it was allowed to crystallize at room temperature. Brown crystals of single crystal X-ray diffraction quality were obtained in 4–5 days. The X-ray intensity data for [Cu(L¹)₂] were collected on a Xcalibur, Eos, Gemini diffractometer equipped with a graphite monochromated Cu K α radiation ($\lambda = 1.54184$). The crystal (complex **1**) used for data collection was of dimensions 0.30 \times 0.20 \times 0.20 mm³. The cell dimensions were determined by a least-squares fit of the angular settings of 8923 reflections in the θ range 4.45 $<$ 71.83°. The intensities were measured by ρ and ω scan modes for the θ range 3.11 $<$ 65.00°. The structure was solved by direct methods using SHELXS97²⁶. All non-H atoms of the molecule were located in the best E map. Full-matrix least-squares refinement was carried out using SHELXL97²⁶. All H atoms were included as idealized atoms riding on the respective C atoms with C-H bond lengths appropriate to the C-atom hybridization. The final refinement cycles converged to $R = 0.0431$ and $R_w (F^2) = 0.1183$ for the observed data. Residual electron densities ranged from -0.263 to 0.370 e \AA^{-3} . Atomic scattering factors were taken from International Tables for X-ray Crystallography (1992, Vol. C, Tables 4.2.6.8 and 6.1.1.4). The crystallographic data are summarized in Table 1.

Catalytic reactions :

Oxidation of benzyl alcohol :

Catalytic oxidation of benzyl alcohol was carried out in a 50 mL round bottom flask fitted with a water circulated condenser using copper(II) complexes of Schiff bases of 4-acylpyrazolone ligands as a catalyst. In a typical reaction, benzyl alcohol, catalyst and 30% H₂O₂ were intensively stirred at the 90 °C temperature for the whole duration of the reaction. After completion of the reaction, reaction mixture was concentrated on rotary evaporator. Hexane was added to the system, and the organic phase was separated. By this simple procedure, isolation of the carbonyl product in the organic phase was achieved.

Oxidation of styrene :

Catalytic oxidation of styrene was carried out in a 50 mL round bottom flask fitted with a water circulated con-

denser using copper(II) complexes of Schiff bases of 4-acylpyrazolone ligands as a catalyst. In a typical reaction, styrene, catalyst and 30% H₂O₂ were intensively stirred at the 80 °C temperature for the whole duration of the reaction. After completion of the reaction, reaction mixture was concentrated on rotary evaporator. Hexane was added to the system, and the organic phase was separated. By this simple procedure, isolation of the carbonyl product in the organic phase was achieved.

Conclusion

The single crystal X-ray analysis of copper complex of Schiff base of acylpyrazolone derivative reveals that the copper(II) complexes of Schiff bases of acylpyrazolone derivatives can also exist in the planar quadrilateral geometry. The synthesized copper complexes were used as homogeneous catalysts for the solvent free oxidation of styrene and benzyl alcohol. The complexes were found to be successful in the oxidation of styrene and benzyl alcohol to benzaldehyde under mild reaction conditions.

Supporting information

CCDC 1007668 contains the supplementary crystallographic data for the complex **1**. This data can be obtained free of charge at www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/conts/retrieval.html or from the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Center, 12 Union Road, Cambridge CB2 1EZ, UK; Fax : 44-1223/336033. E-mail : deposit@ccdc.ac.uk.

Acknowledgement

RNJ is thankful to the UGC, New Delhi (India) for financial support [F.37-376/2009, 12.01.2010(SR)]. SP is thankful to UGC, New Delhi (India) for the UGC-BSR fellowship.

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